

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Navigating the Globalisation of the Digital Economy: The Construction and Challenges of the Legal Framework for Cross-Border Personal Information Transfer in Uzbekistan

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Abstract

Uzbekistan's Personal Data Act, which came into force in 2019, represents a significant legislative advancement in the nation's data protection landscape and aims to align with international standards. The law establishes fundamental principles for personal data processing, grants data subjects essential rights, and defines obligations for data controllers, thereby forming an initial legal framework for the development of the digital economy. However, its provisions remain relatively general, and specific implementing regulations and enforcement practices—particularly regarding cross-border personal data flows—require further refinement. Challenges such as unclear alternative mechanisms, limited practical guidance, and potentially complex approval procedures create uncertainties for enterprises engaged in international operations. This study proposes recommendations for improving Uzbekistan's legal framework and institutional arrangements for cross-border personal data transfers, drawing on judicial practice and legislative developments.

Keywords: Personal information; Cross-border flow; Digital sovereignty; Flexible regulation; Regional mutual recognition.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary era of rapid digital economic globalisation, the cross-border flow of personal information has become a highly contested global issue. Legal questions related to data flow rules, regulatory authorities, and the scope of personal information directly affect individual rights, corporate development, public interests, economic growth, and national security.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

1. Legal framework and cross-border rules: flexible practices within rigid structures

Uzbekistan's personal information protection system is centred on the 2019 Personal Data Act (Law No. ZRU-547), which constitutes the country's first comprehensive regulation of personal data processing. Article 2 defines personal data broadly and applies to most processing activities, while exempting non-commercial household use, state secrets, and certain law enforcement activities.

The 2021 amendment (Law No. ZRU-666) introduced strict data localisation requirements. Article 27-1 mandates that enterprises processing personal data of Uzbek citizens utilise domestic technical infrastructure and register relevant databases in the State Register of Personal Databases. This provision has had significant implications for multinational digital platforms.

Sector-specific legislation further differentiates regulatory practices. Financial institutions, healthcare providers, and telecommunications operators face additional restrictions on cross-border data transfers. Compared with the EU's GDPR, Uzbekistan adopts a more restrictive negative-list approach and imposes substantially lower administrative penalties, limiting deterrence.

Institutionally, regulatory oversight was historically exercised by the State Personalisation Centre, later replaced in 2024 by the Personnel Research Agency under the Ministry of Justice. Uzbekistan also participates in regional and international data governance initiatives, including cooperation within the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation and observer participation in the Eurasian Economic Union.

Despite these efforts, international assessments highlight challenges related to operational feasibility, transparency, and compliance costs, particularly for foreign enterprises.

2. Practical constraints and systemic reform

Technical capacity constraints, regulatory ambiguity, and limited transparency continue to hinder effective governance. Data localisation policies have increased operational costs and reduced foreign investment in the ICT sector. To address these issues, authorities are exploring a tiered data classification system and enhanced regional cooperation, including the proposed Central Asian Digital Single Market initiative.

Technological self-reliance is also being promoted through domestic encryption development and regional satellite cooperation projects, aimed at strengthening digital sovereignty while enhancing competitiveness.

Conclusion

Firstly, detailed rules under the Personal Data Protection Act should be revised to clarify consent requirements, incorporate modern data governance principles, and provide practical compliance guidance for cross-border transfers.

Secondly, regulatory capacity should be strengthened through the adoption of regulatory technology tools, electronic filing systems, and risk-based supervision mechanisms.

Thirdly, regional mutual recognition mechanisms should be advanced through the development of Central Asian data governance standards.

Finally, deeper international cooperation is required to balance digital sovereignty with economic openness and to secure a stronger voice for developing economies in global digital governance.

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